

Antibacterial properties of aluminium, magnesium/nickel co-doped zinc oxide nanoparticles

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Abstract : The present examination aimed to prepare $Zn_{0.90}Al_{0.05}Mg_{0.05}O$ and $Zn_{0.90}Al_{0.05}Ni_{0.05}O$ nanoparticles by soft chemical method. The antibacterial activity of the prepared samples was probed against *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Salmonella typhimurium* and *Klebsiella pneumoniae*. The structure of the samples was confirmed through powder XRD technique as hexagonal wurtzite. The size of the particles was found in between 11–20 nm. The capsule like formation was observed in SEM images. The incorporation of Al/Mg/Ni in zinc oxide lattice was verified with absorption peaks found at 780 cm^{-1} and 823 cm^{-1} in the FTIR spectra of samples a and b. The increases in permeability of membrane brought a change in activity of cell membranes and offer the cell death with the effect of nanoparticles.

Keywords : ZnO nanoparticles, XRD, SEM, antibacterial activity, soft chemical method.

Introduction

Nanotechnology is most active technology in material science. Nanotechnology is an emerging area for manufacturing new materials at the nano scale. Zinc oxide nanoparticles are multifunctional materials at the nano scale. Zinc oxide nanoparticles are n-type semiconductors with hexagonal wurtzite structure¹. Zinc oxide nanoparticles have a high surface-to-volume ratio, good electronic properties and increased activity². The co-doping of elements with zinc oxide nanoparticles enhances their properties. The elements such as Mg, Al³ and Ni, Mn⁴ were doped with zinc oxide nanoparticles. The method such as thermal evaporation⁵, microwave method⁶, chemical synthesis⁷ were widely employed for the synthesis of zinc oxide nanoparticles.

Human beings are infected by micro-organism present in their living environment. Researchers have researched for the development of cost effective antibacterial agents. Zinc oxide nanoparticles are the suitable antibacterial

agents. The antibacterial activity of zinc oxide was probed by many researchers^{8–10}.

The present study has been aimed to prepare aluminium, magnesium/nickel co-doped zinc oxide nanoparticles using soft chemical method. The antibacterial activities of the prepared nanoparticles were tested against the bacterial strains *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Salmonella typhimurium* and *Klebsiella pneumoniae*.

Experimental

Materials and method :

Analytical grade reagents obtained from Merck chemicals were used without further purification. The zinc nitrate hexahydrate $Zn(NO_3)_2 \cdot 6H_2O$ was used as host precursor. The aluminium nitrate nano hydrate $Al(NO_3)_3 \cdot 9H_2O$, nickel nitrate and magnesium nitrate hexahydrate $Mg(NO_3)_2 \cdot 6H_2O$ were used as dopant precursors. The sodium hydroxide and pure de-ionized wa-

ter were used in precursor solutions.

The nanoparticles were prepared by soft chemical method. The precursor solution was allowed for 24 h reaction time at room temperature. The resulting precipitate was purified with de-ionized water. It was dried in air for 3 h for the preparation of nanoparticles. The growth temperature was chosen as 120 °C. The prepared nanoparticles were (a) $\text{Zn}_{0.90}\text{Al}_{0.05}\text{Mg}_{0.05}\text{O}$ and (b) $\text{Zn}_{0.90}\text{Al}_{0.05}\text{Ni}_{0.05}\text{O}$.

Characterization :

Synthesized ZnAlMgO and ZnAlNiO nanoparticles were characterized by XRD analysis, scanning electron microscopy and Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy. The X-ray diffraction patterns of nanoparticles were recorded using X-ray diffractometer (BRUKER) with $\text{CuK}\alpha$ radiation ($\lambda = 1.54060 \text{ \AA}$). Scanning Electron Microscope with EDAX (JEOL) was used to witness the surface morphology of the nanoparticles. Fourier-transform infrared spectrophotometer SHIMADZU (FT-IR 8400) was used to record the FTIR spectra of the prepared nanoparticles.

Antibacterial activity :

Antibacterial activity of ZnAlMgO and ZnAlNiO nanoparticles were tested against the bacterial strains *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Salmonella typhimurium* and *Klebsiella pneumoniae* by disk diffusion method. The diameter of zone of inhibition of the sample was obtained.

Results and discussion

XRD analysis :

Fig. 1 shows the XRD patterns of ZnAlMgO and ZnAlNiO nanoparticles synthesized by soft chemical method. The XRD spectral analysis uncovered that the samples were crystallized in hexagonal wurtzite structure with space group P63mc (JCPDS and number 80-0075). All the observed reflections in the spectra were in line with the JCPDS data. The presence broadened diffraction peaks showed the formation of excellent nanoparticles. The absence of a diffraction peak linked with Al/Mg/Ni pointed that the doping of Al/Mg/Ni has not altered the structure of zinc oxide⁴. The lattice parameters were estimated using eqs. (1) and (2)¹.

$$a = \frac{\lambda}{\sqrt{3}} (\sin \theta_{100}) \quad (1)$$

$$c = \frac{\lambda}{\sin \theta_{102}} \quad (2)$$

where, λ and θ were wavelength of X-ray and Bragg angle of the diffraction peak.

The derived values of a and c were agreed well with standard values ($a = 3.253 \text{ \AA}$, $c = 5.206 \text{ \AA}$, JCPDS card no. 80-0075). The c/a ratio values exposed that the prepared nanoparticles were high-quality crystalline structure. The calculated unit cell volumes were synchronized

Fig. 1. XRD spectra of nanoparticles : (a) $\text{Zn}_{0.90}\text{Al}_{0.05}\text{Mg}_{0.05}\text{O}$, (b) $\text{Zn}_{0.90}\text{Al}_{0.05}\text{Ni}_{0.05}\text{O}$.

well with reported values ($V = 47.77 \text{ \AA}$ for JCPDS card no. 80-0075). The lattice shrinkage was found in samples a and b when compared with the standard. This shrinkage occurred with the incorporation of aluminum/magnesium/nickel in zinc oxide lattice.

Table 1. Parameters estimated from XRD data

Sample	<i>a</i> (\AA)	<i>c</i> (\AA)	<i>c/a</i>	<i>V</i> (\AA ³)	<i>D</i> (nm)
a	3.249	5.206	1.602	47.62	20
b	3.228	5.177	1.603	46.71	11

The average particle size of prepared nanoparticles was calculated by Scherrer equation¹⁰.

$$D = \frac{0.9\lambda}{\beta \cos \theta} \quad (3)$$

where, *D* and β were particle size and full-width at half-maximum respectively. The Gaussian fitting program was used to measure full-width at half-maximum. The average particle size of prepared nanoparticles was found in between 11–20 nm.

SEM analysis :

Fig. 2. shows SEM micrographs of prepared nanoparticles. The SEM analysis of prepared samples probed the surface morphology. The capsule shaped nanorods were observed in samples a and b.

Fig. 2. SEM micrographs of nanoparticles : (a) $Zn_{0.90}Al_{0.05}Mg_{0.05}O$, (b) $Zn_{0.90}Al_{0.05}Ni_{0.05}O$.

The surface agglomeration was found less due to incorporation Ni in sample b. The aggregation of the surface was originated from the high surface energy of the nanoparticles³.

FTIR analysis :

Fig. 3 shows the FTIR spectra of ZnAlMgO and ZnAlNiO nanoparticles synthesized by soft chemical

method. The presence of different chemical functional groups established the formation of nanoparticles. The observed peaks were tabulated in the Table 2. The stretching modes of zinc oxide were confirmed with peaks at 475 and 6512 cm^{-1} of the samples (a and b)⁷. The incorporation of Al/Mg/Ni in zinc oxide lattice was proved with absorption peaks at 780 cm^{-1} and 823 cm^{-1} in the samples (a and b)⁴. The peaks around 1400 cm^{-1} and 3400 cm^{-1} were assigned to OH-bending and OH-stretching modes of vibrations.

Antibacterial studies :

The disc diffusion method was employed in antibacterial studies of prepared nanoparticles. The antibacterial activity of the nanoparticles was tested against the strains

Fig. 3. FTIR spectra of nanoparticles : (a) $Zn_{0.90}Al_{0.05}Mg_{0.05}O$, (b) $Zn_{0.90}Al_{0.05}Ni_{0.05}O$.

Table 2. Chemical functional groups assignment of FT-IR spectra

Assignment	Functional groups (cm ⁻¹)	
	a	b
Zn-O stretching	475	652
Mg-O/Al-O stretching	780	823
C=O	1062	-
OH-bending	1649	1426
OH-stretching	3456	3460

Staphylococcus aureus, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Salmonella typhimurium* and *Klebsiella pneumoniae*. The zone of inhibition diameter values of the nanoparticles was determined and tabulated in Table 3.

The antibacterial activity mechanism was explained in many research works⁸⁻¹⁰. The entry of nanoparticles in cell membrane was reported for the reason of massive cell death. The prepared nanoparticles were highly reac-

Table 3. Diameter-zone of inhibition of nanoparticles (mm)

Strains	Diameter-zone of inhibition (mm)							
	a				b			
	25	50	75	100	25	50	75	100
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	3	4	6	7	3	4	9	11
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	5	8	11	12	4	8	9	11
<i>Salmonella typhimurium</i>	4	10	12	14	4	5	9	12
<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i>	8	11	12	14	6	9	10	15

tive due to their high surface-to-volume ratio. The formation reactive oxygen species (ROS) were responsible for the increase in the permeability of the cell membrane. The increase in permeability of membrane brought a interruption of activity of cell membrane and enables the cell death. The DNA codes of the micro-organisms were also affected by the nanoparticles⁸. The prepared nanoparticles showed better growth inhibition against the bacterial strains.

The zone of inhibition diameter values was measured for four different concentrations (25, 50, 75 and 100 µg/ml). The bacterial inhibition was increased with an increase in the concentration of nanoparticles. *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* were Gram-positive bacteria. *Salmonella typhimurium* and *Klebsiella pneumoniae* were Gram-negative bacteria. The antibacterial effect of ZnAlMgO was enhanced on *Salmonella typhimurium* than other strains. The antibacterial effect of ZnAlNiO was better on *Klebsiella pneumoniae* than other strains.

Conclusion

The ZnAlMgO and ZnAlNiO nanoparticles were prepared by soft chemical method. The formation of nanoparticles was confirmed by XRD spectral analysis. The particle size was estimated by Scherrer formula. The size of sample b was found 11 nm. The SEM micrographs demonstrated the surface morphology of the prepared nanoparticles. The capsule shaped nanoparticles were observed from SEM images. The FTIR spectra predicted the presence of metal-oxygen bond in the samples a and b. Antibacterial effect of nanoparticles was tested against *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Salmonella typhimurium* and *Klebsiella pneumoniae*. The zone of inhibition was found to be higher for Gram-negative bacterium than the Gram-positive bacterium. The diameter of zone of inhibition was improved with the increase in the concentration. The increase in permeability of membrane enables the cell death. The DNA code of the microorganisms was also affected by the nanoparticles. The prepared nanoparticles showed better growth inhibition against all the bacterial strains.

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